
Frequency of SARS Cov 2 Ig G Antibody in Healthy Vaccinated and Non Vaccinated Health Care Workers in a Tertiary Care Hospital in Pakistan

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Abstract

In Pakistan, nowadays, the third wave of Covid 19 targets a huge population in highly dense areas. Though the vaccination is providing still the prevalence of Covid increase day by day. This study aims to explore the frequency of SARS Cov 2 IgG antibody in healthy vaccinated and non vaccinated health care workers in a tertiary care hospital in Pakistan.

Methodology: This cross sectional study was conducted by the services hospital lahore in 6 weeks. Two major groups were formed according to the status of infectivity that whether or not they were infected with Covid-19. The groups were further divided on the basis of the genders of the individuals. All their data was extracted after having proper informed consent from the subjects by asking them to fill a consent form. . For this study, we developed some inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Results: A total of 40 healthcare workers participates in this research. During the research period, 22 patients were Covid infected. Among these Covid patients majority they were female (63.6%) rest were male. Only 18 healthy participants were available at the time of the research. In Covid participants, 13 had reactive anti spike antibodies which were considered positive for this study. The cut-off value between non-reactive and reactive Igg lies within the range of 1-1.5 for both Covid infected and non-infected patients.

Conclusion: Our study concluded that the development of antispikes antibodies plays a vital role in reducing the risk of Covid-19. Human immunity itself produce antibodies that defeat mild and moderate symptoms.

Keywords

Antibodies, Covid vaccination, Healthcare workers

1. Introduction:

In the end of 2019, a new contagious disease coronavirus emerged out from the city of Wuhan, China. With the 2.2 basic reproductive number, its pathological observations

revealed that it is a single-stranded RNA virus that can rapidly start mutations [1]. The initial findings trace its history with the previous species of infections called 229E, OC43, NL63, and HKU1 which usually produce cold symptoms in human beings [2,3]. Researches indicate that this virus has many similarities with MERS COV and SARS COV which are usually caused by animals and can engage human beings in fatal illness [3]. In many regions of the world, Covid prevalence depicts that in the future this epidemic occasionally occurs targeting low economic areas of world [3,4]. Early symptoms of this deadly virus are very similar to pneumonia and it was hard for physicians to generate a distinguishing line between these two viruses at the initial stage [5]. With the help of CT, imaging physicians observed pulmonary opacity in Covid patients. In the electronic imaging of Bronchoalveolar lavage fluid of Covid patients, researchers observed crown shape virus which was emerging from viral spike peplomers [6]. The rapid transmission of this disease occurs through respiratory droplets and close contact. Some studies claim that it may be transmitted by the faeces of affected patients [7]. Usually, the patients had mild symptoms but in many regions, high mortality ratio of Covid was observed among the old age group [8]. In Italy and Spain majority of the affected patients were from old age groups and poor immune systems and comorbidities encourage the high probability of death among them [9].

After the development of vaccination, researchers are now concerned with the postinfection immunity of the patient that helps to prevent the probability of reinfection among them [10-12]. Now the major concern transformed to analyze the durability of vaccination which leads to cell-mediated immune responses. Anti-spike and anti-nucleocapsid antibodies are defined as defence mechanism for postinfection [13]. Neutralization of these antibodies may produce a strong immunity among the patients. In many mild and moderate infected patients, the chances of reinfection were not highly observed. This means that their body already produces enough amount of antibodies to defend against this deadly virus [14]. In Pakistan, nowadays, the third wave of Covid 19 targets a huge population in highly dense areas. Though the vaccination is providing still the prevalence of Covid increase day by day. This study aims to explore the frequency of SARS Cov 2 IgG antibody in healthy vaccinated and non vaccinated health care workers in a tertiary care hospital in Pakistan.

2. Methodology:

This cross sectional study was conducted by the services hospital lahore in 6 weeks. Two major groups were formed according to the status of infectivity that whether or not they were infected with Covid-19. The groups were further divided on the basis of the genders of the individuals. All their data was extracted after having proper informed consent from the subjects by asking them to fill a consent form. For this study, we developed some inclusion and exclusion criteria.

2.1. Inclusion criteria

For this study, we only select those patients who belong to the 25-55 year age group. There was no occupational restriction. All the healthcare workers from any designation were welcomed to voluntarily participate in this research. Before injecting vaccination they were fully aware of its side effects. Total two doses were injected which were certified by the Government of Pakistan. Their blood samples were taken twice, after the first and second dose of vaccination to evaluate the production of Igg antibodies twice. All the serological samples were sent to the hospital laboratory where serological investigation take place with the help of anti-trimeric spike IgG enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) and anti-nucleocapsid.

2.2. Exclusion criteria

All the pregnant healthcare staff was excluded from the research.

Patients with severe Covid symptoms and who need mechanical ventilation were also excluded from the study.

For result analysis, healthcare workers were classified according to their baseline characteristics. Those non- Covid patients who show non-reactive (negative) Igg were considered at risk of infection and Igg were considered at risk of reinfection after 60 days. We used the Poisson regression model to evaluate the baseline antibody status for incidence over time, age and gender. We further investigated anti-nucleocapsid antibody to evaluate the combined three antibody assay.

3. Results

A total of 40 healthcare workers participates in this research. During the research period, 22 patients were Covid infected. Among these Covid patients majority they were female (63.6%) rest were male. Only 18 healthy participants were available at the time of the research. In Covid participants, 13 had reactive anti spike antibodies which were considered positive for this study. The cut-off value between non-reactive and reactive Igg lies within the range of 1-1.5 for both Covid infected and non-infected patients. The median range of participants was observed as 38 years old.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of Covid ad Healthy patients

Variables	N (%)= 40	Mean \pm SD
Covid infected	22 (55%)	11 \pm 4.24
Female	14 (63.6%)	
Male	8 (36.3%)	
Non infected	18 (45%)	9 \pm 9.899
Male	16 (88.8%)	
Female	2 (11.1%)	

Table 2: Frequency of Igg antibodies in Covid Affected and Healthy patients after vaccination

Variables	N (%)	Mean± SD
Covid Vaccinated Patients		
Reactive = 14		2.75± 1.28
4- 10.99	3 (21.1%)	
11- 17.99	3 (21.1%)	
18- 24.99	3 (21.1%)	
25-31.99	1 (7%)	
32-38.99	1 (7%)	
39-45.99	3 (21.1%)	
Non- reactive n= 8		
0- 0.59	5 (62.5%)	
0.6-0.99	3 (37.5%)	
Healthy participants		
Reactive (Healthy vaccinated patients)= 8		4.5 ± 4.04
1-20.99	5 (62.5%)	
21-40.99	1 (12.5%)	
41-60.99	2 (25%)	
Non reactive (Healthy patients)= 10		
0-0.59	10 (100%)	
0.6-0.99	0	

Figure 1. Levels of IgG in individuals after vaccination

3.1 Discussion

This longitudinal cohort study was conducted to examine the activation of anti spike antibodies to reduce the risk of PCR confirmed coronavirus. In this study, we also examine and compare the production of anti spike antibodies among vaccinated and non vaccinated healthcare workers over 6 weeks of follow up. In non-Covid vaccinated cases, we observed that only 5 cases show Igg reactive results which means that previous virus associated with SARS help them to protect against reinfection for at least 6 months. We further include the postinfection immunity evidence of covid positive vaccinated patients and examined them through anti-nucleocapsid IgG and a combination of anti-nucleocapsid and anti spike Igg which was used as the marker of the previous infection.

During observations, we found an inverse relationship of Sars Covid incidents and baseline anti spike and anti-nucleocapsid antibodies. We further examined that in the non-covid vaccinated group majority of the patients had non-reactive Igg which predicts that their immune system was relatively protected from the infection. In 22 healthcare workers with the Covid PCR test, we observed that their antibodies were declined after vaccination, they were set to ensure high specificity at the time of testing. In two Covid positive workers, we revealed that they had imperfect nature of baseline antibodies after the vaccination. Further examination revealed that those two patients had a history of other chest infection in a recent year. Comparing the results of our study to the worldwide literature on the efficacy of Covid vaccination we observed many similarities. Symptomatic Covid positive patients showed a high intensity of antibodies after vaccination [16]. It also reduces the transmission of virus to other healthy individuals. In recent months, studies based on United States [17], European [18], Israel [19] population revealed that two doses of mRNA covid-19 vaccination have an effective impact on both asymptomatic and symptomatic cases. In the United States, vaccine show 89% effective results for healthy individuals and in Covid positive patients they observed 60% chance of speedy recovery which lower the rate of hospitalization than an unvaccinated person. Similarly, the Pfizer-BioNTech vaccine had an 86% recovery ratio in above 80 years old patients who were infected in the United Kingdom.

The study conducted in Israel revealed that the Pfizer-BioNTech vaccine produces four folds of antibodies in vaccinated person as compared to unvaccinated. On the other hand, many other studies demonstrate that the mRNA Covid vaccine may cause a reduction in the neutralization activity of antibody against mutations. In Brazil vaccine demonstrate poor neutralization activity for B.1.35. As compared to the B.1.1.7 reduction in B.1.3.5 was relatively greater [20-23]. The mutation of the virus reflects similar results in terms of spike protein-specific antibody levels and zero response rate when compared with the Brazilian study [24-27]. Till now there is no single opinion computed that resolve the issue for predicting immunogenicity level for the effectiveness of Covid vaccine [28-29].

In our study, all the healthcare workers voluntarily participate in follow up schedule. All the staff who were willing to participate were offered asymptomatic PCR testing before and after the vaccination. The Covid positive staff were then shifted to isolation where they live for 14 days. Initially, the majority of the Covid patients show mild to moderate symptoms which were not needed any serious medical intervention. The serological results were presented to the participants. Staff were told to maintain social distancing and use their equipment. Limited mobility was suggested to positive antibody patients. During the study some healthcare workers withdrawal from it because of their transformation in other hospitals that is why the participation of Covid negative staff was relatively low than the infected one. We suggest producing long term cohort studies that will examine the postinfection immunity with big sample size.

4. Conclusion

Our study concluded that the development of antispikes antibodies plays a vital role in reducing the risk of Covid-19. Human immunity itself produces antibodies that defeat mild and moderate symptoms. Comorbidities like other infections, cardiovascular diseases and diabetes may alter the production of antispikes Igg antibodies.

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